

**University of
East London**

Pioneering Futures Since 1898

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Task 1. The Case Study

I have decided to construct a charity website - Care Unity (www.careunity.freewebhostmost.com), inspired by the exemplary Red Cross organization, which is renowned for working for humanitarian causes. The goal I have set for this project is to develop an easy-to-use website that clearly explains the charitable purpose. This website will be designed with the user's experience in mind, ensuring that anyone who visits can easily understand how they can contribute to and support philanthropic efforts.

Conflicts in places like Gaza and Yemen are stark reminders of the struggles people face. These areas are suffering greatly due to ongoing wars, leaving countless individuals in desperate need of basic necessities and humanitarian aid. For instance, according to figures shown by AJLabs

(2023), The situation in Gaza is very upsetting and has serious effects on the people living there. Over 1.5 million Gazans have been displaced due to the ongoing conflict. Food and water supplies are running perilously low, particularly in the northern region of Gaza. Additionally, the scarcity of fuel is significantly impacting essential services such as water desalination and communication services. Likewise, Yemen is facing a severe crisis. Out of its population, 21.6 million need urgent humanitarian aid. The long-lasting war has caused major issues: 17.3 million are hungry, 20.3 million need health services, and 15.3 million lack access to water BRC (n.d.). Many health facilities are closed, leading to disease outbreaks. Additionally, Yemen is dealing with extreme weather and economic problems BRC (n.d.).

Therefore, keeping these conflicts in mind, the global community's support is crucial in these times to provide relief and hope to those affected by such crises. My main reason for creating this website is to offer help to people around the world who are in similar harsh situations. Though the content on the website won't necessarily focus on conflicts in Gaza and Yemen, it will highlight our mission and vision services for those who are in similar situations and how their donations can create significant positive changes in their lives by providing access to food, water, healthcare, and other essential requirements.

I will design the following pages for Care Unity:

- Homepage: To display the stats, our partners, and a short mission summary.
- About Us page: To provide information about our organization, mission, and vision motifs.
- Campaigns: To highlight the various mission services we provide.
- Contact: For visitors to get in touch with us by submitting their inquiries, feedback, or support requests.
- Donation page: This will redirect the user to a placeholder page stating "This page is under construction".
- Legal pages: Pages such as privacy policy, cookies policy, and terms & conditions.

By breaking it down into distinct sections, each with a clear and concise purpose, the website's structure becomes more straightforward to understand for visitors.

Task 2. Background Research

2.1 Review of Charity Websites

Website	Design	Usability	Accessibility	Legal Requirements
<p>1. Redcross United States - https://www.redcross.org/</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On the landing page, we could see the big bold message, "You Can Make a Difference" reflecting the mission of this charity website. As we scroll down, we see the image of a man promoting gift cards for the donors, so we know the website accepts donations as well as offering gift card options for people who want to contribute more tangibly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The website design is user-centric with a clear and organized layout. Navigation is made straightforward with a top menu bar featuring essential links like "Donate", "Give Blood", and "Volunteer". 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The color contrast and text size of the website suggest that the site is designed to be accessible to everyone. The website is also available in Spanish, making it accessible to more people. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal requirements for the website include privacy policies, terms of service, and compliance with accessibility standards. The website does not prompt for the cookie policy for users to manage their cookie preferences.

<p>2. Make A Wish - https://www.make-a-wish.org.uk/</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The design has a clean and modern look, with a visually appealing front section featuring a video background and a clear call-to-action to the "Donate" button in the navigation and the "Donate now and make wishes come true" button in the middle. • The typography is easy to read, with a suitable font size and weight. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website has a simple navigation, with a "Menu" button for accessing additional content and links. • The main call-to-action buttons ("Donate" and "Donate now and make wishes come true") are displayed on the front and are easy to find. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having text on a moving video can be hard to read for people with sight problems or learning difficulties because the words may not stand out enough. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website complies with relevant data protection and privacy laws, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the UK. • A cookie editing policy is also present.
<p>3. Bowel Cancer UK - https://www.bowelcanceruk.org.uk/</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website has a clean and modern design with a clear layout. The use of colors, such as the teal and yellow accents, is visually appealing and helps draw attention to important elements like the donation buttons and call-to-action prompts. • The image used conveys a positive, supportive message. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The navigation menu at the top is clear and easy to understand, allowing users to quickly access different sections of the site. • The donation options are prominently displayed, making it easy for users to contribute should they wish for it. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The font size and contrast mentioned could impact readability for users with visual impairments. • Alt text for the front image is not present. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website complies with basic legal requirements, such as displaying a privacy policy and terms of use links in the footer.

<p>4. Young Minds - https://www.youngminds.org.uk/</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website's design is modern and simple, with lots of space. It uses bright greens, and yellows, which promotes UI. • The homepage of the website has a strong message, "You are not alone," and a welcoming picture of different young people. It creates a good mood and shows what the website stands for right away. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website uses easy-to-read titles like "Latest real stories," "Frequently asked questions," and "More ways to support us" to help visitors find what they need fast. • Calls to action (CTAs) like "Get help and advice" and "Become a YoungMinds Activist" are placed all over the site to encourage people to get involved and use the services offered. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The colors used to make the text clear against the background, which helps people with vision problems or color blindness read more easily. • I have noticed a few parts have used difficult words or technical language that can make it hard for people with learning disabilities or those who don't read well. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The privacy policy link at the bottom of the page shows that the organization adheres to data protection laws like the GDPR in the UK and Europe.
<p>5. British Red Cross - https://www.redcross.org.uk/</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website follows a minimalist and clean design approach, making effective use of whitespace and hierarchy to guide the user's attention. • The website uses red and white colors a lot, which matches the British Red Cross's style and makes it easier for people to recognize the brand. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website has a clear main menu that makes it easy to find important parts. • The way the content is arranged and the overall design is well-planned, with similar topics put together in a way that is easy to navigate. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website is designed to change its layout and content to fit different screens and devices well. • One thing that could be improved is the contrast between text and background colors to make sure that people with visual impairments can read the text easily. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privacy policy and terms of use show that the website is legally ethical. • It also holds the right permissions for pictures and fonts from third parties to not break copyright rules.

<p>6. Disasters Emergency Committee - https://www.dec.org.uk/</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The first thing I noticed upon lading the website is striking images. It really helps highlight the different humanitarian efforts and emergencies that are being promoted. • Also from my perspective, adding more white space and organizing the content better can make the website easier to read and help users focus on the most important parts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The homepage contains big buttons and clear links that can help users navigate the website easily. • Some parts of the page could be filtered correctly. It would make it easier for users to find the specific information they're looking for quickly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upon noticing, I would prefer to tweak the color contrast of a few sections in the second half of the homepage. • The website could be navigated through the keyboard. This makes sure everyone can use the website. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website complies with basic legal requirements, such as displaying a privacy policy and terms of use. • They also enforce copyright rules. No one can use or share anything shown for business purposes without getting permission from DEC first.
<p>7. Fema - https://www.fema.gov/</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website looks good and is well-organized. Everything appears to be in its place for a modern design charity website. • It uses pictures and colors that reflect Charitie's serious role in emergencies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website has a smart menu that helps you find your way easily on mobile devices. • A geo-filtering option at the top helps show you news and content based on your location. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website is made so everyone, including people with disabilities, can use it. They follow laws and regulations to make sure of this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Similar to other aforementioned charity websites, Fema has a privacy policy, terms of use, and civil rights.

<p>8. SOS Children Villages International - https://www.sos-childrensvillages.org/</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The layout is well-structured, with clear sections for different types of content, making it easy to navigate and find information. • The color scheme is appropriate, but I think the overuse of blue hues throughout the website appears monotonous and lacks visual interest. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The charity uses consistent labeling and categorization (e.g., "Our Work," "Resources," "Take Action") which demonstrates the content hierarchy. • The website's language options are not immediately visible, which could be an issue for users who prefer to browse in a language other than English. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Though most of the elements are perfectly accessible, some design elements, like the usage of the thin white-coloured font on images, could potentially pose accessibility challenges for users with visual impairments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The inclusion of a privacy policy link in the footer suggests that the organization recognizes the importance of data protection and privacy regulations.
<p>9. ALIMA - https://alima.ngo/en/home/</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The front background picture pictures shows well how ALIMA is dedicated to helping people get healthcare where it's tough to do so, which is what they aim to do. • But there's a catch, the text overlaid on the background image may be difficult to read for users with visual impairments or on smaller screens. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The donation message popped up right away when I visited the website. It seemed too pushy and interrupted my browsing. • Even though getting donations is very important for non-profit groups, being asked for money too soon might stop visitors from looking through the website and make them less likely to give. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There's a lack of contrast between the text and the background image. This makes it difficult for users with visual impairments to read. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Though there is a privacy policy and cookie policy, there are no Terms of Service mentioned in the entire website.

<p>10. Action Aid - https://actionaid.org/</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website adopts a bold and striking visual style, with prominent use of red and black colors. The color scheme is consistent with ActionAid's branding and sparks a sense of urgency and importance to their cause. • The design could be improved by incorporating more white space as a few sections of the current layout feel somewhat cluttered. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website is easy to navigate. The top menu clearly shows the main parts like "Our Work," "Where We Work," and "Latest News." 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The color contrast between text and background seems great. • Suboptimal typography for longer text sections affects readability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website includes a privacy policy and a cookie policy, indicating compliance with data protection and privacy regulations.
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2.2 Summary

Going through the multiple charity websites that are more or less the same as mine, I gained a few insights into the best practices and areas for improvement in website design, usability, accessibility, and legal compliance.

Most themes I observed have something in common - they are made with the user's needs in mind. Websites with clean designs, attractive colors, easy navigation, clear CTAs, and GDPR compliance, like the British Red Cross and Young Minds, stood out for effectively communicating their mission. Some websites had room for improvement, with issues like low color contrast, excessive use of images or videos affecting readability, and cluttered layouts,

potentially lowering accessibility quality for users with disabilities. Likewise, aggressive donation prompts without context about the charity's work might also discourage user engagement. Concerning legal, most charities have privacy policies and terms of use, but some lack essential information such as cookie policies.

In essence, I think, it's important for charity websites to prioritize a balance between visually appealing designs, clear messaging, and accessibility to increase User Experience (UI). Ensuring compliance with legal requirements and ethical standards is essential for building trust with both donors and beneficiaries.

Task 3. Web Planning

3.1 Pages Designing

Before coding for Care Unity, I'll design different page wireframes to decide on the elements and their placement. The tool that I used to create wireframes is Visily (see appendix).

A) Header

I'll start the design with the header since it will be the same across my website.

B) Footer

After the header, the next section that is going to be common across all pages is the footer.

C) Homepage

D) About Us page

Section 1

This section is essentially about “Who We Are” which will cover key achievements, and the impact the website made in the community.

Heading 1

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Heading 2

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Fugiat ipsum ut voluptate non proident ullamco. Dolor ad adipiscing laborum sit reprehenderit laboris labore officia consectetur ipsum ullamco Lorem. Nulla qui paratur id nunc commodo Lorem reprehenderit Lorem fugi.

Section 2

This section will feature images that enhance the story of our impact.

Section 3

This section will cover the mission and vision values of the charity website.

E) Campaigns

Section 1
This section highlights the campaigns, outlining various initiatives launched to drive change and make a difference.

Campaigns

Duis magna qui dui labore etiam enim ut aliquam sceleris do enim tempor ex labore delectant enim. Dolori qui tempor labore veniam aute sunt proident enim aliquam velit. Aute laborum nulla labore eu incididunt illum paucis velit non assumenda ad reprehenderit sint. Cupiditate officia aute consectetur voluptate enim incididunt tempor enim connohio ut iure. Duis culpa ad labore laborum illum fugiat.

Fugiat enim labore enim do nostrum aliquam delectant nihil aute ad cupiditate labore. Tempor non do incididunt exercitation ut eu dui enim nostrum. Aliqua est est aliquam labore exercitation labori enim ad. Duis per iure nulla est fugiat dolor et eu nihil tempor deserunt. Duis et enim dolore eu amet iure mollis. Idemque iure velit. Duis mollis aliqua aute cupiditate nisi amet cupiditate conseqat enim do ut iure. Duis est labore amet nostrum labore veniam dui. Sit aliquam tempor reprehenderit enim do veniam reprehenderit.

Subheading

Capital amet laborum do qui enim Lorem fugiat eu labore reprehenderit.

Capital amet laborum do qui enim Lorem fugiat eu labore reprehenderit.

Capital amet laborum do qui enim Lorem fugiat eu labore reprehenderit.

Capital amet laborum do qui enim Lorem fugiat eu labore reprehenderit.

Capital amet laborum do qui enim Lorem fugiat eu labore reprehenderit.

Capital amet laborum do qui enim Lorem fugiat eu labore reprehenderit.

Donate Now text, with the button

Section 2
This sections showcase images that vividly depict website mission services.

Section 3
A donate button after a donate text.

F) Contact Us page

Section 1

A contact heading which will have the contact details such as phone numbers and email address.

Section 2

A embedded Google Map to display the location of the Care Unity organization

G) Donation page

The donation page that will show the message, "Donate page is under construction". This will let the user know that the page is in the development process.

H) Legal pages

The Legal section contains three parts: Cookies Policy, Privacy Policy, and Terms and Conditions. The legal agreements will be generated by a popular legal agreements generator for websites and apps - TermsFeed (see appendix), and will be added to the site using HTML. They will be styled to match the website's fonts and colors.

3.2 Navigations Design

I decided to use a flat navigational structure for the website. The "Index" functions as a central hub, with all the main pages linked directly to it in a flat, single-level manner. The structure

consists of the Homepage, About Us, Campaigns, Contact, Donation Page, Privacy Policy, Cookies Policy, and Terms and Services - all sitting at the same level. All pages are immediately accessible, requiring no extra clicks. The reason for choosing this structure is to enhance clarity and organization: It provides a clear and logical organization of pages, making it easier for users to understand the website's structure and navigate through the content (Lin, 2017).

3.3 Color Scheme

A) Header

The header uses a dark background color (**#23282d**), white text color (**#fff**) for good contrast and readability, and a vibrant blue color (**#3858e9**) for a call-to-action element such as a button that stands out from the rest of the header.

B) Footer

The footer will have a vibrant blue background color (**#3858e9**) to draw attention; white text and form fields (**#fff**) for clear readability against the colorful background; and a dark button color (**#23282d**) to make the call-to-action button prominently visible within the footer area. The footer color scheme is a bit of an inverse compared to the header, but by using the same vibrant blue shade (**#3858e9**) as the header button, it maintains a cohesive brand identity and visual consistency throughout the website.

C) Body

The body's color scheme will adapt dynamically based on the specific page and elements. For instance, in the campaigns page, the card borders will be a light gray shade (**#d3d3d3**), Meanwhile, the card text will appear on a slightly transparent gray background (**#8a8a8a1a**), to give it an elegant style.

All colors used in the body are:

3.4 Overview

I will adapt the **modular approach** to build my site, beginning with the development of the header and footer. Thereafter, I will start to design the homepage, which is divided into four distinct sections as I planned in the wireframe design. Then, using JavaScript, I will integrate the HTML document of the header and footer into the homepage, and subsequently, apply the same method across all other pages.

The main **web technologies** I'll be using for the website are HTML for content addition and CSS for design. I'll also use JavaScript to implement the header and footer across all pages for uniformity. This is because any design changes in the header or footer can be made just once and

will automatically update site-wide. Additionally, I'll use Visual Studio Code (see appendix) to efficiently manage my folders and images during the coding and testing phases.

The website will have a **straightforward URL**. I plan to use the free hosting service Webhostmost (see appendix), which provides 125MB of storage. This should suffice for my charity website, which will have less number of pages and media. The website can be accessed at <https://careunity.freewebhostmost.com/>.

Task 4: Implementation and Testing

4.1 Header

A) Care Unity Logo - This is the site's logo, which I made on Canva (see appendix). It's white to stand out on the black background.

B) Navigation Links - These are the menu items that turn a different color when you hover over them. They're white on a dark background, making them easy to find and click. This enhances usability and accessibility.

C) Search Bar - Just a basic search bar that's there for decorative purposes only.

D) Donate Button - It's a blue button that stands out against the dark black background. When the user hovers over it, it pops out a bit, hinting that the user can click it to go to the donation page.

Header W3C report

- Error** Element `head` is missing a required instance of child element `title`.
From line 8, column 1 to line 8, column 7
`der.css"></head></body>`
Content model for element `head`:
If the document is an `iframe_srcdoc document` or if title information is available from a higher-level protocol: Zero or more elements of `metadata content`, of which no more than one is a `title` element and no more than one is a `base` element.
Otherwise: One or more elements of `metadata content`, of which exactly one is a `title` element and no more than one is a `base` element.
- Error** Bad value `Images/Care Unity .png` for attribute `src` on element `img`: Illegal character in path segment: space is not allowed.
From line 13, column 13 to line 13, column 53
``
- Error** The element `button` must not appear as a descendant of the `a` element.
From line 32, column 35 to line 32, column 60
`ate.html"><button class="donatebtn">Donate`

4.2 Footer

The footer has a dark blue background with white color for texts and a black colored button in the form. This color scheme, layout, and element placement make it easy for the user to use and read the content.

A) Care Unity Logo - Displays the Charity's logo for brand recognition.

B) Subscription Form - Collects emails, but it's just for decorative purposes right now.

C) Contact Info - Lists physical address, email, and social media links. More details are on the contact page.

D) Legal Links - Directs to Cookies, Privacy Policy, and Terms pages. I wanted to keep Legal Pages separate from the main navigation in the header.

E) Copyright and Credit - Indicates that I, Deepak Kumar designed the site, with a link to my LinkedIn profile for professional visibility.

Footer W3C report

1. **Info** Trailing slash on void elements has no effect and interacts badly with unquoted attribute values.
From line 7, column 5; to line 7, column 49
1.0"><<link rel="icon" href="Images/favicon.ico" /> ..

2. **Error** Element `head` is missing a required instance of child element `title`.
From line 9, column 1; to line 9, column 7
ter.css"></head><body
Content model for element `head`:
If the document is an `iframe srcdoc` document or if title information is available from a higher-level protocol: Zero or more elements of `metadata content`, of which no more than one is a `title` element and no more than one is a `base` element.
Otherwise: One or more elements of `metadata content`, of which exactly one is a `title` element and no more than one is a `base` element.

3. **Error** Bad value `Images/Care Unity .png` for attribute `src` on element `img`: Illegal character in path segment: space is not allowed.
From line 20, column 21; to line 20, column 81

4. **Error** Bad value `Terms and Conditions.html` for attribute `href` on element `a`: Illegal character in path segment: space is not allowed.
From line 61, column 21; to line 61, column 56
Terms

5. **Error** End tag for `body` seen, but there were unclosed elements.
From line 79, column 1; to line 79, column 7
</div></body></ht

6. **Error** Unclosed element `div`.
From line 13, column 5; to line 13, column 24
ody><<div class="footer">

4.3 Homepage

Section A: Since it's the first thing a visitor would see in this section, I used a simple layout with a bold heading and a brief message encouraging participation as a volunteer. The stats box helps show Charity's work using numbers. The hand image is an attractive visual element giving a friendly vibe. The high-contrast text and image ensure good accessibility.

Section B: This section displays the logos of various partner organizations in a simple grid layout. This is to build credibility as a Charity Organization. Additionally, the logos have a good contrast against the background.

Section C: This section has a minimalistic layout with a centered heading and two paragraphs of text describing the charity's impact. It also links to the campaigns page thus it includes functionality. Plus, the high-contrast text and enough white space provide good readability.

Section D: This section includes a bold heading and a large blue "Donate here" button, as a call-to-action for donations. The donate button links to the donation page. Furthermore, as the user hovers on it, the button pops out a little and the cursor changes to the pointer.

Homepage W3C report

```
1. Info Trailing slash on void elements has no effect and interacts badly with unquoted attribute values.  
From line 8, column 5 to line 8, column 49  
n --> <link rel="icon" href="Images/favicon.ico" /> ⚠
```

```
2. Error Bad value Images/World Health Organization.jpeg for attribute src on element img: Illegal character in path segment: space is not allowed.  
From line 59, column 13 to line 59, column 68  
⚠
```

```
3. Error Bad value Images/Medicines & Healthcare products Regulatory Agency.png for attribute src on element img: Illegal character in path segment: space is not allowed.  
From line 60, column 13 to line 60, column 91  
⚠
```

```
4. Error Bad value Images/The Health Foundation.png for attribute src on element img: Illegal character in path segment: space is not allowed.  
From line 62, column 13 to line 62, column 63  
⚠
```

```
5. Error Bad value Images/Cancer Research UK.png for attribute src on element img: Illegal character in path segment: space is not allowed.  
From line 63, column 13 to line 63, column 60  
⚠
```

```
6. Warning The document is not mappable to XML 1.0 due to two consecutive hyphens in a comment.  
At line 93, column 27  
ame 4 below -->⚠ <sectio
```

4.4 About Us Page

Section A: In the first section, I designed it keeping simplicity and clarity in mind. For instance, the text is aligned to the left-right format and presented in a readable font size, to ensure a comfortable reading experience. The emoji of the United Kingdom 🇬🇧 subtly hints at the country the Charity is located at. In terms of functionality, this section does not include any interactive elements.

Section B: In this section, I aimed to include images to visually represent the charity's work. Three images are arranged in a row with the same aspect ratio. The the user over the images, they bulge out. The contrast between the images and the dark background is decent as well.

Section C: The layout of this section is consistent with section A, which maintains a cohesive design throughout the page. I included the content in clearly and logically, with the mission statement followed by the vision statement. Additionally, the black-colored text has a good contrast against the white background.

About Us W3C report

```
1. Info Trailing slash on void elements has no effect and interacts badly with unquoted attribute values.
From line 7, column 5; to line 7, column 49
1.0"><link rel="icon" href="Images/favicon.ico" />

2. Warning Section lacks heading. Consider using h2-h6 elements to add identifying headings to all sections, or else use a div element instead for any cases where no heading is needed.
From line 60, column 5; to line 60, column 34
01><section class="About-images">

3. Error End tag section: seen, but there were open elements.
From line 107, column 5; to line 107, column 14
/></section>

4. Error Unclosed element div.
From line 80, column 9; to line 80, column 38
<div class="thinblackline2">
```

4.5 Campaigns Page

Section 1: Similar to the About Us page, I tried to design the campaign similarly to maintain consistency. I used the white space and clear section divisions to make it visually appealing and organized layout. As far as content is concerned, the text is informative and tells the user about the organization's dedication to making a difference in people's lives.

Section 2: Here, I showcased the mission services of Care Unity as a grid of visually appealing cards. Each card displays an image and a brief description of a mission service. All the cards are of the same height and width, and they adapt themselves according to the screen size.

Section 3: From a functionality perspective, after showing Charity's mission services just above, the "Donate Now" button is hard to miss and encourages visitors to take action.

Overall, in my opinion, the accessibility is great since dark-colored text is used against light backgrounds, and there is a clear hierarchy of information on the campaign page.

Campaigns page W3C report

1. **Info** Trailing slash on void elements has no effect and interacts badly with unquoted attribute values.
From line 7, column 5: to line 7, column 48
1.0"><<link rel="icon" href="Images/favicon.ico"/>

2. **Error** End tag section seen, but there were open elements.
From line 60, column 5: to line 60, column 14
/div><</section>

3. **Error** Unclosed element div.
From line 22, column 9: to line 22, column 35
<div class="thinblackline">

4. **Error** Bad value Images/Disaster Relief .jpeg for attribute src on element img: Illegal character in path segment: space is not allowed.
From line 72, column 17: to line 72, column 63

5. **Error** Bad value Images/Blood Services.webp for attribute src on element img: Illegal character in path segment: space is not allowed.
From line 84, column 17: to line 84, column 61

6. **Error** Bad value Images/Armed Forces .webp for attribute src on element img: Illegal character in path segment: space is not allowed.
From line 96, column 17: to line 96, column 60

7. **Error** Bad value Images/Training services .webp for attribute src on element img: Illegal character in path segment: space is not allowed.
From line 109, column 17: to line 109, column 65

8. **Error** Bad value Images/International Services .webp for attribute src on element img: Illegal character in path segment: space is not allowed.
From line 120, column 17: to line 120, column 70

9. **Error** Bad value Images/Volunteer Services.webp for attribute src on element img: Illegal character in path segment: space is not allowed.
From line 133, column 17: to line 133, column 65

4.6 Contact Page

Since there should be nothing much on the contact page other than contact information, I decided to present it in a simple, text-based format with clear headings and subheadings.

Section A: Here, on the left, the contact info has an easy-to-read font and color style, making it visually accessible. The layout is straightforward, and the contact information is organized into logical categories.

Section B: This section is mainly about embedding the Google Map with the organization’s address in it. This could highly be useful for residents of London, where the organization’s address is based. The map adds usability to find and navigate to the physical address. As for the functionality, users can zoom in and zoom out. Furthermore, the map is responsive based on the device screen size.

Contact page W3C report

- Info** Trailing slash on void elements [has no effect](#) and [interacts badly with unquoted attribute values](#).
From line 7, column 5 to line 7, column 49
`1.0"><link rel="icon" href="Images/favicon.ico" />`
- Error** End tag `section` seen, but there were open elements.
From line 76, column 5 to line 76, column 14
`/div></section>`
- Error** Unclosed element `div`.
From line 22, column 9 to line 22, column 35
`<div class="thinblackline">`
- Warning** Section lacks heading. Consider using `h2-h6` elements to [add identifying headings to all sections](#), or else use a `div` element instead for any cases where no heading is needed.
From line 16, column 5 to line 16, column 30
`iv><section class="heading1">`

4.7 Donate Page

Since the donation page is under construction, as it says, I tried to keep the design minimalist. A solid blue background with large white text did the work. Also, the smiley emoji shows the message is friendly and users should come back later.

Donate page W3C report

```
1. Info Trailing slash on void elements has no effect and interacts badly with unquoted attribute values.
   From line 6, column 5 to line 6, column 49
   1.0"><<link rel="icon" href="Images/favicon.ico" /><

2. Warning Section lacks heading. Consider using h2-h6 elements to add identifying headings to all sections, or else use a div element instead for any cases where no heading is needed.
   From line 12, column 5 to line 12, column 33
   /div><<section class="donate-page"><
```

4.8 Legal Pages

The website has three essential legal pages: the Privacy Policy, Cookies Policy, and Terms & Conditions. They were generated using Termsfeed, a reputable service known for creating legal agreements. Once generated, the HTML provided by Termsfeed was embedded directly into the website. To ensure that these pages align with the overall design aesthetic of the site, I made minor modifications to the HTML. All Legal pages have a similar design and text alignments.

The screenshots of the Legal Pages are mentioned below.

A) Privacy Policy Page

Privacy Policy

Last updated: May 10, 2024

This Privacy Policy describes Our policies and procedures on the collection, use and disclosure of Your information when You use the Service and tells You about Your privacy rights and how the law protects You.

We use Your Personal data to provide and improve the Service. By using the Service, You agree to the collection and use of information in accordance with this Privacy Policy. This Privacy Policy has been created with the help of the [Privacy Policy Generator](#).

Interpretation and Definitions

Interpretation

The words of which the initial letter is capitalized have meanings defined under the following conditions. The following definitions shall have the same meaning regardless of whether they appear in singular or in plural.

Definitions

For the purposes of this Privacy Policy:

- **Account** means a unique account created for You to access our Service or parts of our Service.
- **Affiliate** means an entity that controls, is controlled by or is under common control with a party, where "control" means ownership of 50% or more of the shares, equity interest or other securities entitled to vote for election of directors or other managing authority.
- **Company** (referred to as either "the Company", "We", "Us" or "Our" in this Agreement) refers to Care Unity , 2 Mortlake Road, IG1 2SX.
- **Cookies** are small files that are placed on Your computer, mobile device or any other device by a website, containing the details of Your browsing history on that website among its many uses.
- **Country** refers to: United Kingdom

B) Cookies Policy Page

Cookies Policy

Last updated: May 10, 2024

This Cookies Policy explains what Cookies are and how We use them. You should read this policy so You can understand what type of cookies We use, or the information We collect using Cookies and how that information is used. This Cookies Policy has been created with the help of the [Cookies Policy Generator](#).

Cookies do not typically contain any information that personally identifies a user, but personal information that we store about You may be linked to the information stored in and obtained from Cookies. For further information on how We use, store and keep your personal data secure, see our Privacy Policy.

We do not store sensitive personal information, such as mailing addresses, account passwords, etc. in the Cookies We use.

Interpretation and Definitions

Interpretation

The words of which the initial letter is capitalized have meanings defined under the following conditions. The following definitions shall have the same meaning regardless of whether they appear in singular or in plural.

Definitions

For the purposes of this Cookies Policy:

- **Company** (referred to as either "the Company", "We", "Us" or "Our" in this Cookies Policy) refers to Care Unity , 2 Mortlake Road, IG12SX.
- **Cookies** means small files that are placed on Your computer, mobile device or any other device by a website, containing details of your browsing history on that website among its many uses.
- **Website** refers to Care Unity , accessible from careunity.freewebsitehost.com
- **You** means the individual accessing or using the Website, or a company, or any legal entity on behalf of which such individual is accessing or using the Website, as applicable.

The use of the Cookies

C) Terms and Conditions

Terms and Conditions

Last updated: May 10, 2024

Please read these terms and conditions carefully before using Our Service.

Interpretation and Definitions

Interpretation

The words of which the initial letter is capitalized have meanings defined under the following conditions. The following definitions shall have the same meaning regardless of whether they appear in singular or in plural.

Definitions

For the purposes of these Terms and Conditions:

- **Affiliate** means an entity that controls, is controlled by or is under common control with a party, where "control" means ownership of 50% or more of the shares, equity interest or other securities entitled to vote for election of directors or other managing authority.
- **Country** refers to: United Kingdom
- **Company** (referred to as either "the Company", "We", "Us" or "Our" in this Agreement) refers to Care Unity , 2 Mortlake Road, IG125X .
- **Device** means any device that can access the Service such as a computer, a cellphone or a digital tablet.
- **Service** refers to the Website.
- **Terms and Conditions** (also referred as "Terms") mean these Terms and Conditions that form the entire agreement between You and the Company regarding the use of the Service. This Terms and Conditions agreement has been created with the help of the [Terms and Conditions Generator](#).

Third party Social Media Services means any services or content (including data, information, products or services) provided by a third party that may be displayed, included or made available by the

Task 5: Evaluation and Reflection

I think I have done a decent job coding the Care Unity website. I tried to include information and design elements inspired by the top charity websites I researched in Task 2. For example, I focused on creating a clean and user-friendly design, with a combination of both dark and light color palettes, ensuring good accessibility and usability, and incorporating essential functionality.

However, there is always room for improvement. Many of the top charity sites I analyzed during doing Task 2 had interactive elements powered by JavaScript, such as email subscription forms, donation calculators, and interactive maps or event calendars. Therefore, this is something I could have worked on to increase user experience. Perhaps, next time!

Search Engine Optimization (SEO)

According to Goodwin (2023), SEO, short for Search engine optimization, involves improving the website to rank higher in search engine results on web browsing sites like Google and Bing. This helps more people find a site when they search for what you offer. One thing that helps

webpages to have better SEO exposure is using semantic HTML (Montti, 2024). This involves using HTML tags that give meaning to the content, like <header>, <footer>, <article>, and <section>. And in my website, I have incorporated them.

However, to extend my reach and connect with a larger audience, I would have to focus on the various other aspects of SEO, one of them being mobile accessibility, which is discussed below.

Mobile Accessibility

According to Statista (2020), approximately 58.67% of internet users surf the web on mobile. Therefore, it could be said that how important it becomes to have a mobile-optimized website theme. Firstly, it improves the user interface (UI), making it easier and more pleasant for people to use. Better UI leads to longer visit times and lower bounce rates, which search engines see as signs of an authority site (L, 2023). Even though I couldn't add many CSS keyframes to my website this time, it's something I plan to do for my future projects.

Advertising Revenues

I understand that as a non-profit organization, securing sustainable funding is crucial to ensure the continuity of our vital services and initiatives. There are a few ways to monetize the Charity and the brand itself. Firstly, I could implement targeted online advertising campaigns on our website and social media platforms. For that, I could offer advertising space on our website, especially to other businesses who share the same cause as ourselves. Plus, I could make use of Google Ads (see appendix) to reach a wider audience and promote our mission. Additionally, organizing fund-raising events and letting other likewise businesses advertise at the event might help bring extra revenue as well.

Local Exposure

Since Care Unity is based in London, there are certain things we can do to make people aware of our charity. Firstly, events like charity fairs or awareness days might help to have one-to-one

conversations with people. Secondly, we could also team up with local businesses like restaurants, shops, and other stores. We could put the posters outside the store or near the checkout tills. Furthermore, partnering with local schools, universities, and churches can allow us to share our mission through their communication channels as well.

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Appendix

A) Websites

Here are the websites I used for the report and to get content such as pictures:

1. Pexels: Free stock photos and videos for creative projects.
2. Canva.com: Online graphic design and editing platform.
3. Webhostmost.com: Web hosting service provider.
4. VisualStudio: Code editor for developers by Microsoft.
5. Visily: Wireframe editor tool.
6. Termsfeed: To generate legal policies and terms for websites.
7. Google Ads: Google's advertising platform for online campaigns.

B) Screenshots of Code

Header HTML and CSS

```
1 <!DOCTYPE html>
2 <html lang="en">
3
4 <head>
5     <meta charset="UTF-8">
6     <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
7     <link rel="icon" href="Images/favicon.ico" />
8     <link rel="stylesheet" href="CSS/header.css">
9 </head>
10
11 <body>
12     <header class="header">
13         <div class="websiteLogo">
14             
15         </div>
16         <nav class="navMenu">
17             <!-- Navigation menu links to the different pages of the website. -->
18             <ul class="navList">
19                 <li><a class="navLink" href="homepage.html">Home</a></li>
20                 <li><a class="navLink" href="about.html">About</a></li>
21                 <li><a class="navLink" href="campaigns.html">Campaigns</a></li>
22                 <li><a class="navLink" href="contact.html">Contact</a></li>
23             </ul>
24         </nav>
25
26         <div class="searchBar">
27             <form>
28                 <input type="text" placeholder="Search...">
29                 <button><i class="fa fa-search"></i></button>
30                 
31             </form>
32
33         </div>
34         <div>
35             <a href="donate.html"><button class="donatebtn">Donate Now</button></a>
36         </div>
37
38     </header>
39 </body>
40 </html>
```

```

1  /*
2  * Import the Inter font family from Google Fonts.
3  */
4  @import url("https://fonts.googleapis.com/css2?family=Inter:wght@100..900&display=swap");
5
6  * {
7    margin: 0;
8    padding: 0;
9    font-family: "Inter", sans-serif;
10 }
11
12 /* Hide horizontal scrollbar on the entire page */
13
14 .header {
15   width: 100%;
16   position: relative;
17   border-radius: 2px;
18   background-color: #23282d;
19   border: 1px solid rgba(255, 255, 255, 0.1);
20   box-sizing: border-box;
21   height: 75px;
22   overflow: hidden;
23   text-align: left;
24   font-size: 12px;
25   color: #fff;
26 }
27
28 .websiteLogo {
29   position: absolute;
30   top: 19px;
31   left: 34px;
32 }
33
34 .websiteLogo img {
35   width: 180px;
36   filter: invert(1); /*change the color of the logo to white*/
37   margin: 0 auto;
38 }
39
40 .navList {
41   list-style: none;
42   display: flex;
43   justify-content: center;
44   align-items: center;
45   gap: 30px;
46   color: #fff;
47   font-size: 18px;
48   width: 25vw;
49   position: absolute;
50   top: 25px;
51   left: 210px;
52 }
53
54 .navLink {
55   text-decoration: none;
56   color: white;
57   font-family: "Inter", sans-serif;
58   font-size: 18px;
59 }
60
61 .navLink:hover {
62   color: #ccc;
63   transform: scale(1.1);
64 }
65
66
67 .navLink:hover {
68   cursor: pointer;
69 }

```

Footer HTML and CSS

```

1 <!DOCTYPE html>
2 <html lang="en">
3
4 <head>
5   <meta charset="UTF-8">
6   <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
7   <link rel="icon" href="Images/favicon.ico" />
8   <link rel="stylesheet" href="CSS/footer.css">
9 </head>
10
11 <body>
12
13   <div class="footer">
14
15     <div class="footerContainer">
16
17       <div class="footerLeft">
18
19         <div class="footer-siteName">
20           
21         </div>
22
23         <!-- This is the email subscription form for the website -->
24         <div class="email-box">
25           <p>Stay up to date</p>
26           <form action="#" method="POST">
27             <!-- Email address input field -->
28             <input type="email" id="email" name="email" placeholder="Enter your email address..." required>
29             <!-- Submit button for the form -->
30             <div class="email-submit">
31               Subscribe
32             </div>
33           </form>
34         </div>
35
36       </div>
37       <div class="footerRight">
38         <div class="contactDetails">
39           <div>Contact</div>
40           <div>2 Mortlake Road,
41             London
42             IG1 2XS</div>
43           <div>careunity@info.com</div>
44         </div>
45         <div class="socialIcons">
46           
47           
48           
49           
50         </div>
51       </div>
52
53       <div class="linebreak">
54
55     </div>
56
57     <div class="footercopyright">
58
59
60     <div class="legals">
61       <a href="cookies.html">Cookies</a>
62       <a href="privacy.html">Privacy Policy</a>
63       <a href="Terms and Conditions.html">Terms & Conditions</a>
64     </div>
65
66
67     <div class="sitecopyright">
68       Copyright © 2024 Care Unity | All rights reserved
69     </div>
70
71
72     <!-- Inline CSS below -->
73
74     <div class="made-in-lodon">
75       Made with ♥ in London by <a class="Deepak-Kumar" href="https://www.linkedin.com/in/einsstark"
76         style="text-decoration: underline; cursor: pointer; color: white;">Deepak Kumar</a> 😊
77     </div>
78
79   </div>
80

```



```

1  <!-- Import url from fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Inter&subset=latin,latin-ext -->
2
3  <!-- Root element -->
4  * {
5    margin: 0;
6    padding: 0;
7    font-family: "Inter", sans-serif;
8  }
9
10 <!-- HTML -->
11 <!-- Root element -->
12 <!-- Body -->
13 body {
14   font-family: "Inter", sans-serif;
15 }
16
17 .font {
18   background-color: #f9f9f9;
19   color: white;
20   height: 100px;
21   width: 100%;
22   display: flex;
23   flex-wrap: wrap;
24   flex-direction: column;
25 }
26
27 .font-container {
28   display: flex;
29   flex-direction: row;
30   flex-wrap: wrap;
31   justify-content: space-around;
32   align-items: center;
33 }
34
35 .font-item {
36   display: flex;
37   flex-wrap: wrap;
38   flex-direction: column;
39   justify-content: center;
40   align-items: flex-start;
41   padding: 8px;
42   margin: 8px;
43   width: 45%;
44 }
45
46 .font-item-label {
47   font-size: 14px;
48   width: 100%;
49   margin-left: 20px;
50 }
51
52 .font-item-box {
53   background-color: #d9d9d9;
54   display: flex;
55   padding: 20px;
56   border-radius: 8px;
57   margin-left: 20px;
58   justify-content: center;
59   /* Additional styling of
60   margin-left: 40px;
61   width: 90%;
62   flex-direction: column;
63 }
64
65
66 .font-item-box-p {
67   margin-bottom: 20px;
68   color: white;
69   font-size: 24px;
70 }
71
72
73 .font-item {
74   width: 100px;
75   font-size: 18px;
76 }
77
78
79 .font-item-box-button {
80   width: 100%;
81   padding: 20px;
82   margin-bottom: 10px;
83   border: 1px solid #ccc;
84   border-radius: 8px;
85 }
86
87
88 .font-item-box-button {
89   padding: 10px 20px;
90   background-color: #e91e63;
91   color: #fff;
92   border: none;
93   border-radius: 8px;
94   cursor: pointer;
95 }
96
97 .font-item-button {
98   background-color: #e91e63;
99 }
100
101 .font-item {
102   padding: 10px 20px;
103   background-color: #f9f9f9;
104   width: 100%;
105   font-size: 18px;
106   margin-left: 10px;
107   font-style: "Inter", sans-serif;

```

Homepage HTML and CSS

```
1 <DOCTYPE html>
2 <html lang="en">
3 <head>
4 <meta charset="UTF-8">
5 <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
6 <title> Home </title>
7 <link href="css/style.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css">
8 <script src="js/main.js"></script>
9 </head>
10 <body>
11 <div class="header">
12 <div class="container">
13 <div class="row">
14 <div class="col-12">
15 <div class="text">
16 <h1> Home </h1>
17 </div>
18 </div>
19 </div>
20 </div>
21 <div class="main">
22 <div class="container">
23 <div class="row">
24 <div class="col-12">
25 <div class="text">
26 <h2> Home </h2>
27 </div>
28 </div>
29 </div>
30 </div>
31 <div class="footer">
32 <div class="container">
33 <div class="row">
34 <div class="col-12">
35 <div class="text">
36 <p> Home </p>
37 </div>
38 </div>
39 </div>
40 </div>
41 </body>
42 </html>
```

```

1  A small red(1) and blue(2) paper(3) is(4) on(5) the(6) table(7) in(8) the(9) room(10).
2
3  /
4  / width: 90;
5  / padding: 0;
6  / margin: 0 auto;
7  / text-align: center;
8  /
9  /
10 /
11 /
12 /
13 /
14 /
15 /
16 /
17 /
18 /
19 /
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About Us page HTML and CSS

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1 <!DOCTYPE html>
2 <html lang="en">
3
4 <head>
5   <meta charset="UTF-8">
6   <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
7   <link rel="icon" href="Images/favicon.ico" />
8   <title>About Us</title>
9   <link rel="stylesheet" href="CSS/about.css">
10 </head>
11
12 <body>
13
14   <div id="headerContainer"></div>
15
16   <section class="heading1">
17
18     <h1 class="text1">
19       Who We Are
20     </h1>
21
22     <div class="thinblackline">
23
24       <div class="text2">
25         <div class="text2-left">
26
27           <div>
28             We are a team of change-makers who believe that every helping hand can provide relief and support to
29             those in crisis.
30           </div>
31
32           <div>
33
34             Care Unity is not a government agency. Care Unity is a registered 501(c)(3) nonprofit organization that depends on volunteers and the generosity of people of the United Kingdom to deliver its mission.
35           </div>
36
37         </div>
38
39         <div class="text2-right">
40           <div class="text2-right-p1">Every single day, an abundance of compassionate souls, individuals who
41             resonate with the values of Care Unity, extend their heartfelt compassion to those grappling
42             with adversity. Together, within our interconnected network of benefactors, volunteers, and
43             dedicated team members, we rally around a shared mission: to alleviate suffering, fostering hope
44             and resilience on both local and global scales.</div>
45
46           <div class="text2-right-p2">We now run shelter homes, schools and a reasonable mess that helps such
47             needy young people. We also have our helpline offices spread throughout the country so one can
48             approach us anytime they need help.</div>
49
50         </div>
51       </div>
52     </div>
53
54   </section>
55
56   <section class="About-Images">
57
58     <div class="image1">
59       
60     </div>
61
62     <div class="image2">
63       
64     </div>
65
66     <div class="image3">
67       
68     </div>
69
70   </section>
71
72   <section class="heading2">
73
74     <h2 class="text3">
75       Our Approach
76     </h2>
77
78     <div class="thinblackline2">
79
80       <div class="text4">
81         <div class="text4-left">
82           <div>Our Mission</div>
83
84           <div>
85             At Care Unity, our mission is to extend compassion and support to those facing adversity, both locally and globally.
86           </div>
87
88           <div>
89             Through our network of donors, volunteers, and dedicated team members, we strive to alleviate suffering, foster resilience, and empower communities to confront challenges with confidence.
90           </div>
91
92           <div class="text4-right">
93             <div>Our Vision</div>
94
95             <div>
96               Our vision at Care Unity is to create a world where every individual, including those affected by environmental crises, receives the support they need to thrive.
97             </div>
98
99             <div>
100               We envision a future where compassion, empowerment, and solidarity extend to all, ensuring that those impacted by environmental challenges find solace and assistance on their path to resilience and recovery.
101             </div>
102
103           </div>
104         </div>
105       </div>
106     </section>
107
108   <div id="footerContainer"></div>
109
110   <script>
111     const headerContainer = document.getElementById("headerContainer");
112
113     fetch("header.html")
114       .then(response => response.text())
115       .then(html => headerContainer.innerHTML = html)
116       .catch(error => console.error(error));
117   </script>
118
119   <script>
120     const footerContainer = document.getElementById("footerContainer");
121
122     fetch("footer.html")
123       .then(response => response.text())
124       .then(html => footerContainer.innerHTML = html)
125       .catch(error => console.error(error));
126   </script>
127 </body>
128 </html>

```



```

1 *data-cs="url" href="/forms.googleusercontent.com/css?family=Inter:wght@900,950&display=swap"
2
3 {
4   width: 400px;
5   padding: 20px;
6   box-sizing: border-box;
7   font-family: "Inter", sans-serif;
8 }
9
10
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Campaigns page HTML and CSS

Contact Us page

```
1 <!DOCTYPE html>
2 <html lang="en">
3
4 <head>
5   <meta charset="UTF-8">
6   <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
7   <link rel="icon" href="images/favicon.ico" />
8   <title>Contact Us | i11o</title>
9   <link rel="stylesheet" href="css/contact.css">
10 </head>
11
12 <body>
13   <div id="headerContainer"></div>
14
15
16   <section class="heading">
17
18     <div class="text">
19       Contact
20     </div>
21
22     <div class="buttonContainer">
23
24       <div class="button">
25         <div class="text-left">
26           </div>
27
28         <div>
29           Way to reach Care Unity.
30         </div>
31
32         <div class="phone-numbers">
33
34           <div class="email-address">
35             <small email="open class="underLineOver">careunity@info.com</small>
36           </div>
37
38           <div> Phone number listings:
39           </div>
40           <div> <small>Main Phone Number: +44 800 733 2767</small></div>
41           <div> <small>Training/Certification Issues: +44 800 733 2767 > </small> "Training & Certification"</div>
42           <div> <small>Employment Verification: +44 800 367 5690 (code: 28022)</small></div>
43           <div> <small>Employment 007 Verifications: Secure ofax +44 224 649 8217</small></div>
44           <div> <small>Vendors (for existing vendors only): +44 888 316 4895</small></div>
45
46           <div> <small>If you are a vendor/supplier looking to partner with Care Unity, please <a
47             class="underLineOver" href="contact.html">click here.</a>
48           </small>
49           <div class="educational-purposes">
50             <small>The number listed above is for educational purposes only. These are not official numbers.
51           </small>
52           </div>
53
54           <div class="text-right">
55             </div>
56
57           <div>
58             <small>Map Address:
59           </small>
60
61           <div class="map-container">
62
63             <iframe
64               src="https://www.google.com/maps/embed?hl=en&map=1a33134271a31350400.9994528461431208.87312832280887943051.549888877876312a311812f81f31a3121113241212681433.113a313a21a4847a8a669a9751cf184f88de61a78531a121a2 NorthLake Rd, Elford, ST1, ST14 5LH, UK" data-bbox="125 505 837 525"
65               loading="lazy" referrerpolicy="no-referrer-when-downgrade"
66             >
67             </iframe>
68             <small>Map of map container
69           </small>
70           </div>
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```

```

1 @import url("https://fonts.googleapis.com/css2?family=Inter:wght@100..900&display=swap");
2
3 * {
4   margin: 0;
5   padding: 0;
6   box-sizing: border-box;
7   font-family: "Inter", sans-serif;
8 }
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18 html {
19   overflow-x: hidden;
20 }
21
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```

Donate Page

```
1 <!DOCTYPE html>
2 <html lang="en">
3 <head>
4   <meta charset="UTF-8">
5   <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
6   <link rel="icon" href="Images/favicon.ico" />
7   <title>Donate</title>
8   <link rel="stylesheet" href="CSS/donate.css">
9 </head>
10 <body>
11   <div id="headerContainer"></div>
12   <section class="donate-page">
13     <div>
14       Donate page is under construction 😊
15     </div>
16     <div>Please come back later.</div>
17   </section>
18
19
20   <script>
21     const headerContainer = document.getElementById('headerContainer');
22
23     fetch('header.html')
24       .then(response => response.text())
25       .then(html => headerContainer.innerHTML = html)
26       .catch(error => console.error(error));
27
28   </script>
29 </body>
30 </html>
```

```
1 @import url("https://fonts.googleapis.com/css2?family=Inter:wght@100..900&display=swap");
2
3 * {
4   margin: 0;
5   padding: 0;
6   box-sizing: border-box;
7   font-family: "Inter", sans-serif;
8 }
9
10 html {
11   overflow-x: hidden;
12 }
13
14 body {
15   overflow-x: hidden;
16 }
17
18 .donate-page{
19   width: 100%;
20   height: 100vh;
21   display: flex;
22   flex-wrap: wrap;
23   flex-direction: column;
24   align-items: center;
25   justify-content: center;
26   background-color: rgb(56, 88, 233);
27   font-family: "Inter", sans-serif;
28   position: relative;
29   font-size: 70px;
30   color: white;
31   text-align: center;
32 }
33
34 .donate-page :nth-child(2){
35   font-size: 30px;
36   color: white;
37   text-align: center;
38   font-style: "Inter", sans-serif;
39   margin-top: 10px;
40 }
```

Privacy Policy HTML and CSS

```

1 <!DOCTYPE html>
2 <html lang="en">
3
4 <head>
5   <meta charset="UTF-8">
6   <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
7   <link rel="icon" href="Images/favicon.ico" />
8   <title>Privacy Policy</title>
9   <link rel="stylesheet" href="CSS/privacy.css">
10 </head>
11
12 <body>
13
14   <!-- The below section contains the privacy policy generated by TermsFeed.com -->
15
16   <div id="headerContainer"></div>
17
18   <section class="privacy">
19
20
21     <h1>Privacy Policy</h1>
22     <p>Last updated: May 10, 2024</p>
23     <p>This Privacy Policy describes Our policies and procedures on the collection, use and disclosure of Your
24       information when You use the Service and tells You about Your privacy rights and how the law protects You.
25     </p>
26     <p>We use Your Personal data to provide and improve the Service. By using the Service, You agree to the
27       collection
28       and use of information in accordance with this Privacy Policy. This Privacy Policy has been created with the
29       help of the <a href="https://www.termsfeed.com/privacy-policy-generator/" target="_blank">Privacy Policy
30       Generator</a>.</p>
31     <h2>Interpretation and Definitions</h2>
32     <h3>Interpretation</h3>
33     <p>The words of which the initial letter is capitalized have meanings defined under the following conditions.
34       The
35       following definitions shall have the same meaning regardless of whether they appear in singular or in
36       plural.
37     </p>
38     <h3>Definitions</h3>
39     <p>For the purposes of this Privacy Policy:</p>
40     <ul>
41       <li>
42         <p><strong>Account</strong> means a unique account created for You to access our Service or parts of our
43           Service.</p>
44       </li>
45       <li>
46         <p><strong>Affiliate</strong> means an entity that controls, is controlled by or is under common control
47           with a party, where &quot;control&quot; means ownership of 50% or more of the shares, equity
48           interest or
49           other securities entitled to vote for election of directors or other managing authority.</p>
50       </li>
51       <li>
52         <p><strong>Company</strong> (referred to as either &quot;the Company&quot;, &quot;We&quot;,
53           &quot;Us&quot;
54           or &quot;Our&quot; in this Agreement) refers to Care Unity , 2 Mortlake Road, IG1 2SX.</p>
55       </li>
56       <li>
57         <p><strong>Cookies</strong> are small files that are placed on Your computer, mobile device or any other
58           device by a website, containing the details of Your browsing history on that website among its many
59           uses.</p>
60       </li>
61       <li>
62         <p><strong>Country</strong> refers to: United Kingdom</p>
63       </li>
64       <li>
65         <p><strong>Device</strong> means any device that can access the Service such as a computer, a cellphone
66           or a
67           digital tablet.</p>
68       </li>
69       <li>
70         <p><strong>Personal Data</strong> is any information that relates to an identified or identifiable
71           individual.</p>
72       </li>
73       <li>
74         <p><strong>Service</strong> refers to the Website.</p>
75       </li>
76       <li>
77         <p><strong>Service Provider</strong> means any natural or legal person who processes the data on behalf
78           of
79           the Company. It refers to third-party companies or individuals employed by the Company to facilitate
80           the
81           Service, to provide the Service on behalf of the Company, to perform services related to the Service
82           or

```



```
1 @import url("https://fonts.googleapis.com/css2?family=Inter:wght@100..900&display=swap");
2
3 /* General styles */
4 * {
5   margin: 0;
6   padding: 0;
7   box-sizing: border-box;
8   font-family: "Inter", sans-serif;
9 }
10
11 html {
12   overflow-x: hidden;
13 }
14
15 body {
16   overflow-x: hidden;
17   color: #23282d;
18 }
19
20 .privacy {
21   margin: 80px;
22 }
23
24 .privacy h1{
25   text-align: center;
26   font-size: 36px;
27   margin-bottom: 40px;
28 }
29
30 .privacy h1,
31 h2,
32 h3 {
33   color: #23282d;
34 }
35
36 .privacy h1 {
37   text-align: center;
38 }
39
40 .privacy h2,
41 h3 {
42   margin-top: 30px;
43 }
44
45 .privacy h4 {
46   margin-top: 20px;
47 }
48
49 .privacy p {
50   margin-top: 15px;
51   line-height: 1.6;
52 }
53
54 .privacy ul {
55   margin-top: 15px;
56   padding-left: 20px;
57 }
58
59 .privacy a {
60   color: #007bff;
61   text-decoration: none;
62 }
```

Cookies Policy HTML and CSS

```

1 <!DOCTYPE html>
2 <html lang="en">
3
4 <head>
5   <meta charset="UTF-8">
6   <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
7   <link rel="icon" href="Images/favicon.ico" />
8   <title>Cookies Policy</title>
9   <link rel="stylesheet" href="CSS/cookie.css">
10 </head>
11
12 <body>
13
14   <div id="headerContainer"></div>
15
16   <!-- The below section contains the cookies policy generated by TermsFeed.com -->
17
18   <section class="cookies">
19
20
21     <h1>Cookies Policy</h1>
22     <p>Last updated: May 10, 2024</p>
23     <p>This Cookies Policy explains what Cookies are and how We use them. You should read this policy so You can
24       understand what type of cookies We use, or the information We collect using Cookies and how that information
25       is
26       used. This Cookies Policy has been created with the help of the <a
27         href="https://www.termsfeed.com/cookies-policy-generator/" target="_blank">Cookies Policy Generator</a>.
28     </p>
29     <p>Cookies do not typically contain any information that personally identifies a user, but personal information
30       that
31       we store about You may be linked to the information stored in and obtained from Cookies. For further
32       information
33       on how We use, store and keep your personal data secure, see our Privacy Policy.</p>
34     <p>We do not store sensitive personal information, such as mailing addresses, account passwords, etc. in the
35       Cookies
36       We use.</p>
37     <h2>Interpretation and Definitions</h2>
38     <h3>Interpretation</h3>
39     <p>The words of which the initial letter is capitalized have meanings defined under the following conditions.
40       The
41       following definitions shall have the same meaning regardless of whether they appear in singular or in
42       plural.
43     </p>
44     <h3>Definitions</h3>
45     <p>For the purposes of this Cookies Policy:</p>
46     <ul>
47       <li><strong>Company</strong> (referred to as either &quot;the Company&quot;, &quot;We&quot;, &quot;Us&quot;;
48         or
49         &quot;Our&quot; in this Cookies Policy) refers to Care Unity , 2 Mortlake Road, IG12SX.</li>
50       <li><strong>Cookies</strong> means small files that are placed on Your computer, mobile device or any other
51         device by a website, containing details of your browsing history on that website among its many uses.
52     </li>
53       <li><strong>Website</strong> refers to Care Unity , accessible from <a href="careunity.freewebhostmost.com"
54         rel="external nofollow noopener" target="_blank"> careunity.freewebhostmost.com</a></li>
55       <li><strong>You</strong> means the individual accessing or using the Website, or a company, or any legal
56         entity
57         on behalf of which such individual is accessing or using the Website, as applicable.</li>
58     </ul>
59     <h2>The use of the Cookies</h2>
60     <h3>Type of Cookies We Use</h3>
61     <p>Cookies can be &quot;Persistent&quot; or &quot;Session&quot; Cookies. Persistent Cookies remain on your
62       personal
63       computer or mobile device when You go offline, while Session Cookies are deleted as soon as You close your
64       web
65       browser.</p>
66     <p>We use both session and persistent Cookies for the purposes set out below:</p>
67     <ul>
68       <li>
69         <p><strong>Necessary / Essential Cookies</strong></p>
70         <p>Type: Session Cookies</p>
71         <p>Administered by: Us</p>
72         <p>Purpose: These Cookies are essential to provide You with services available through the Website and
73           to
74           enable You to use some of its features. They help to authenticate users and prevent fraudulent use
75           of
76           user accounts. Without these Cookies, the services that You have asked for cannot be provided, and
77           We
78           only use these Cookies to provide You with those services.</p>
79       </li>
80       <li>
81         <p><strong>Functionality Cookies</strong></p>
82         <p>Type: Persistent Cookies</p>

```



```
1 @import url("https://fonts.googleapis.com/css2?family=Inter:wght@100..900&display=swap");
2
3 * {
4   margin: 0;
5   padding: 0;
6   box-sizing: border-box;
7   font-family: "Inter", sans-serif;
8 }
9
10 html {
11   overflow-x: hidden;
12 }
13
14 body {
15   font-family: "Inter", sans-serif;
16   padding: 0;
17   box-sizing: border-box;
18   overflow-x: hidden;
19   color: #23282d;
20 }
21
22 .cookies{
23   margin: 80px;
24 }
25
26
27 .cookies h1, h2, h3 {
28   color: #23282d;
29 }
30
31 .cookies h1 {
32   text-align: center;
33   font-size: 36px;
34   margin-bottom: 40px;
35 }
36
37 .cookies h2, h3 {
38   margin-top: 30px;
39 }
40
41 .cookies h4{
42   margin-top: 20px;
43 }
44
45
46 .cookies p {
47   margin-top: 15px;
48   line-height: 1.6;
49 }
50
51 .cookies ul {
52   margin-top: 15px;
53   padding-left: 20px;
54 }
55
56 .cookies a {
57   color: #007bff;
58   text-decoration: none;
59 }
60
61 .cookies a:hover {
62   text-decoration: underline;
```

Terms and Conditions HTML and CSS

```

1 <!DOCTYPE html>
2 <html lang="en">
3
4 <head>
5   <meta charset="UTF-8">
6   <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
7   <link rel="icon" href="Images/favicon.ico"/>
8   <title>Terms and Conditions</title>
9   <link rel="stylesheet" href="CSS/Terms and Conditions.css">
10 </head>
11
12 <body>
13
14   <div id="headerContainer"></div>
15
16   <!-- The below section contains the Terms and Conditions generated by TermsFeed.com -->
17
18   <section class="terms">
19
20     <h1>Terms and Conditions</h1>
21     <p>Last updated: May 10, 2024</p>
22     <p>Please read these terms and conditions carefully before using Our Service.</p>
23     <h2>Interpretation and Definitions</h2>
24     <h3>Interpretation</h3>
25     <p>The words of which the initial letter is capitalized have meanings defined under the following conditions. The
26       following definitions shall have the same meaning regardless of whether they appear in singular or in plural.
27     </p>
28     <h3>Definitions</h3>
29     <p>For the purposes of these Terms and Conditions:</p>
30     <ul>
31       <li>
32         <p><strong>Affiliate</strong> means an entity that controls, is controlled by or is under common control
33           with a party, where &quot;control&quot; means ownership of 50% or more of the shares, equity interest or
34           other securities entitled to vote for election of directors or other managing authority.</p>
35       </li>
36       <li>
37         <p><strong>Country</strong> refers to: United Kingdom</p>
38       </li>
39       <li>
40         <p><strong>Company</strong> (referred to as either &quot;the Company&quot;, &quot;We&quot;, &quot;Us&quot;
41           or &quot;Our&quot; in this Agreement) refers to Care Unity , 2 Mortlake Road, IG12SX .</p>
42       </li>
43       <li>
44         <p><strong>Device</strong> means any device that can access the Service such as a computer, a cellphone or a
45           digital tablet.</p>
46       </li>
47       <li>
48         <p><strong>Service</strong> refers to the Website.</p>
49       </li>
50       <li>
51         <p><strong>Terms and Conditions</strong> (also referred as &quot;Terms&quot;) mean these Terms and
52           Conditions that form the entire agreement between You and the Company regarding the use of the Service.
53           This Terms and Conditions agreement has been created with the help of the <a
54             href="https://www.termsfeed.com/terms-conditions-generator/" target="_blank">Terms and Conditions
55             Generator</a>.</p>
56       </li>
57       <li>
58         <p><strong>Third-party Social Media Service</strong> means any services or content (including data,
59           information, products or services) provided by a third-party that may be displayed, included or made
60           available by the Service.</p>
61       </li>
62       <li>
63         <p><strong>Website</strong> refers to Care Unity, accessible from <a href="careunity.freewebhostmost.com"
64           rel="external nofollow noopener" target="_blank"> careunity.freewebhostmost.com</a></p>
65       </li>
66       <li>
67         <p><strong>You</strong> means the individual accessing or using the Service, or the company, or other legal
68           entity on behalf of which such individual is accessing or using the Service, as applicable.</p>
69     </li>
70   </ul>
71   <h2>Acknowledgment</h2>
72   <p>These are the Terms and Conditions governing the use of this Service and the agreement that operates between You
73     and the Company. These Terms and Conditions set out the rights and obligations of all users regarding the use of
74     the Service.</p>
75   <p>Your access to and use of the Service is conditioned on Your acceptance of and compliance with these Terms and
76     Conditions. These Terms and Conditions apply to all visitors, users and others who access or use the Service.
77   </p>
78   <p>By accessing or using the Service You agree to be bound by these Terms and Conditions. If You disagree with any
79     part of these Terms and Conditions then You may not access the Service.</p>
80   <p>You represent that you are over the age of 18. The Company does not permit those under 18 to use the Service.</p>
81   <p>Your access to and use of the Service is also conditioned on Your acceptance of and compliance with the Privacy
82     Policy of the Company. Our Privacy Policy describes our policies and procedures on the collection, use and

```



```
1 @import url("https://fonts.googleapis.com/css2?family=Inter:wght@100..900&display=swap");
2
3 * {
4   margin: 0;
5   padding: 0;
6   box-sizing: border-box;
7   font-family: "Inter", sans-serif;
8 }
9
10 html {
11   overflow-x: hidden;
12 }
13
14 body {
15   font-family: "Inter", sans-serif;
16   padding: 0;
17   box-sizing: border-box;
18   overflow-x: hidden;
19   color: #23282d;
20 }
21
22 .terms{
23   margin: 80px;
24 }
25
26
27 .terms h1, h2, h3 {
28   color: #23282d;
29 }
30
31 .terms h1 {
32   text-align: center;
33   font-size: 36px;
34   margin-bottom: 40px;
35 }
36
37 .terms h2, h3 {
38   margin-top: 30px;
39 }
40
41 .terms h4{
42   margin-top: 20px;
43 }
44
45
46 .terms p {
47   margin-top: 15px;
48   line-height: 1.6;
49 }
50
51 .terms ul {
52   margin-top: 15px;
53   padding-left: 20px;
54 }
55
56 .terms a {
57   color: #007bff;
58   text-decoration: none;
59 }
60
61 .terms a:hover {
62   text-decoration: underline;
```